

CURRENT TRENDS AND NATIONAL TRADITIONS IN THE RESTAURANT SERVICES MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN

Sharibaev Rasuljon Nosir oqli
Sharibayev Erkin Yusupjanovich
Muxitdinov Shuhrat Ziyavitdinovich

Namangan Institute of Engineering Technology
rosuljon.sharibayev@mail.ru

Abstract Uzbekistan is a country known for its hospitality, rich cultural heritage, and exquisite cuisine. The country's restaurant services market has been experiencing significant development and changes in recent years. Globalization, rapid technological advancements, and changing consumer needs have led to the emergence of new trends in this sector. This article extensively discusses and analyzes the current trends in the restaurant services market and the impact of national traditions on this market.

Keywords: restaurant business, organization of public catering, management, hospitality, national traditions

1. Introduction

Modern technologies have a significant impact on the restaurant business. Many restaurants are offering online ordering, table reservations, and delivery services through mobile applications and websites. These services help customers save time and provide convenience. Automated systems, such as electronic menus and payment terminals, are being introduced in restaurants. These technologies serve to improve service quality and reduce human errors [1,2].

Uzbek national dishes make up the main part of restaurant menus. Dishes like plov, samsa, manti, and shashlik are highly appreciated not only by the local population but also by tourists. Through national dishes, restaurants strive to preserve their cultural heritage. Hospitality is an integral characteristic of the Uzbek

people and is also manifested in restaurants. The warm attitude of service staff and attention to traditional values play an important role in attracting customers [3].

National patterns, traditional decorations, and elements of folk craftsmanship are used in restaurant interiors. This allows guests to feel the national atmosphere.

2. Technologies and Innovations in the Restaurant Business

Interest in a healthy lifestyle is increasing. Restaurants are adding dietary, vegetarian, and vegan dishes to their menus. This helps to attract a wider range of customers. The trend of using organic and local products is strengthening. This not only improves the quality and taste of dishes but also helps to support local farmers. In the process of globalization, Uzbeks are also showing interest in foreign cuisines. The number of restaurants specializing in Italian, Japanese, Chinese, and Mexican cuisines is increasing. By combining dishes from different cultures, new flavors are being created. This trend is leading to the creation of new and innovative menus in restaurants.

Restaurants are paying attention to environmental protection. They are striving to enhance environmental responsibility by using recyclable materials and implementing energy-saving technologies. To reduce food waste, restaurants are applying effective management systems. This has not only economic benefits but also ecological significance.

Restaurants are strengthening communication with customers through social networks. It has become easier to attract customers by informing them about promotions, news, and special offers. Collaborating with bloggers and influencers on social networks has become an effective marketing tool for restaurants.

3. Modernization of National Traditions

Chefs are creating modern versions of traditional dishes, offering new flavors to customers. Restaurants actively participate in national holidays and festivals, preparing special menus and programs.

According to traditional customs, some restaurants offer separate services for women and men. However, under the influence of modernity, these customs are gradually changing. Family restaurants are focusing on creating an environment comfortable for all family members.

4. Conclusion

The current trends in the restaurant services market are harmoniously combined with national traditions, greatly influencing the development of the sector. Technologies and innovations help to improve service quality, while preserving national traditions allows for the manifestation of cultural characteristics. Interest in healthy eating and environmental responsibility increases the social significance of restaurants.

Restaurants should continue to use modern technologies to create convenience for customers.

It is important to harmonize national dishes and traditions with modernity, offering new experiences to customers.

It is necessary to increase the share of healthy and dietary dishes in menus. Sustainability principles should be implemented, and contributions made to environmental protection.

The customer base can be expanded by strengthening collaboration with social networks and influencers.

The restaurant services market in Uzbekistan is entering a new stage of development as a result of the harmonious combination of national traditions and modern trends. The achievements in this sector make a significant contribution to the country's economic and cultural development.

5. References

1. Borodina V.V., "Restaurant and Hotel Business," Moscow, "Knizhny Mir," 2001.

2. Papiryan G.A., "Management in the Hospitality Industry," Moscow, 2000;
D.I. Abidova, S.R. Safayeva, "Organization of Restaurant Service," Tashkent
– "Iqtisodiyot" – 2019.
3. I. Ivatov, "Restaurant Management," "Iqtisodiyot," TSEU, Tashkent, 2009.